

Appendix I

Within the Markov model used for the decision support system (DSS), the health state “disease free” consists a number of sub-health states, namely no toxicity, or any combination of three different toxicities: rectal bleeding, urinary incontinence and erectile dysfunction. From the models we have available the probability that a patient has one of three different toxicities after a certain amount of time, however we need to transfer this into transition probabilities within our model. To explain how these were calculated please refer to the diagram in Figure A 1 below.

Figure A 1 - The transition probability diagram of the "Healthy" life state. T = all three toxicities; H = no toxicities; T1 = erectile dysfunction; T2 = rectal bleeding; T3 = urinary incontinence; T12 = erectile dysfunction and rectal bleeding; T13 = erectile dysfunction and urinary incontinence; T23 = rectal bleeding and urinary incontinence

Here we see that when patients have a toxicity, they have a probability to recover from toxicity, but they will never get a toxicity if they don't have it initially. We now need to calculate the separate transition probabilities using the probability of a patient recovering from a certain toxicity. First, we convert the probability calculated from the nomograms to the probability per cycle.

P1 = probability of recovering from Erectile dysfunction per cycle

P2 = probability of recovering from Rectal bleeding per cycle

P3 = probability of recovering from Urinary incontinence per cycle

First we will calculate the probability of going from all toxicities to any other health state, as shown in Figure A 2 below.

Figure A 2 - A diagram showing the transition from all toxicities health state to all other health states

The probability of recovering from all three toxicities in one cycle can be obtained using the following relation:

$$\lambda_{T,H} = P1 * P2 * P3$$

The probability of recovering from two different toxicities can be calculated by multiplying the probability of recovering from either toxicity, subtracted by the probability of recovering from all three toxicities.

$$\lambda_{T,T1} = P2 * P3 - \lambda_{T,H}$$

$$\lambda_{T,T2} = P1 * P3 - \lambda_{T,H}$$

$$\lambda_{T,T3} = P1 * P2 - \lambda_{T,H}$$

The probability of recovering from only one toxicity is equal to the total probability of recovering of that toxicity subtracted by the probability of recovering from that toxicity in combination with any other toxicity.

$$\lambda_{T,T23} = P1 - \lambda_{T,T2} - \lambda_{T,T3} - \lambda_{T,H}$$

$$\lambda_{T.T13} = P2 - \lambda_{T.T1} - \lambda_{T.T3} - \lambda_{T.H}$$

$$\lambda_{T.T12} = P3 - \lambda_{T.T1} - \lambda_{T.T2} - \lambda_{T.H}$$

Next we want to calculate the state transition probabilities from a combination of two toxicities to healthy or to a single toxicity, as shown in Figure A 3 below.

Figure A 3 - A diagram showing the state transitions from any combination between two toxicities to the no toxicity health state and a single toxicity health state

The transition probability of any combination of two toxicities to healthy is multiplication of the total probability of recovering of either toxicity:

$$\lambda_{T12.H} = P1 * P2$$

$$\lambda_{T13.H} = P1 * P3$$

$$\lambda_{T23.H} = P2 * P3$$

The probability of recovering from one of the two toxicities is the total probability of recovering from that toxicity subtracted by the probability of recovering from both toxicities.

$$\lambda_{T12.T1} = P1 - \lambda_{T12.H}$$

$$\lambda_{T12.T2} = P1 - \lambda_{T12.H}$$

$$\lambda_{T13.T1} = P1 - \lambda_{T13.H}$$

$$\lambda_{T13.T3} = P3 - \lambda_{T13.H}$$

$$\lambda_{T23.T2} = P2 - \lambda_{T23.H}$$

$$\lambda_{T23.T3} = P3 - \lambda_{T23.H}$$

Finally, the most straightforward transition probability is the probability of recovering from a single toxicity, which is equal to the total probability of recovering from that toxicity, as shown in Figure A 4.

Figure A 4 - The diagram showing the transition from a single toxicity health states to the no toxicity health state

Therefore:

$$\lambda_{T1.H} = P1$$

$$\lambda_{T2.H} = P2$$

$$\lambda_{T3.H} = P3$$

Appendix II

An overview of the utility values, obtained from Steward et al. are shown in Table A 1.

Table A 1- Utility values used in the Markov model

State	Expected value	SD
Post-treatment, no adverse effects	Baseline	-
ED	0.89	0.16
UI	0.83	0.21
RB	0.71	0.26
UI+BT	0.70	0.24
ED+BT	0.57	0.26
ED+UI	0.79	0.23
UI+ED+BT	0.45	0.31
Recurrence	0.81	0.18
Metastatic disease	0.25	0.11

ED: erectile dysfunction; UI: Urinary incontinence; RB: rectal bleeding; SD: standard deviation

An overview of the costs are shown in Table A 2

Table A 2 - Costs used in the Markov model

Description	Mean costs (€)	SD (€)
Open prostatectomy	9780	978
Radiotherapy	8275	827.5
	Mean costs per year (€)	SD (€)
Follow-up (year 1-2)	511	30
Follow-up (year >2)	255	21
Add. costs erectile dysfunction	60	9
Add. costs urinary incontinence	303	21
Add. costs rectal bleeding	95	10
Recurrence	2535	212
Metastatic disease	2288	252
Castrate resistant metastasis	6493	313
SD = standard deviation		

These values were obtained using the care product codes of the relevant treatments. We used the costs published on <https://www.opendisdata.nl>, and we used a standard deviation of 10% of the total costs of the treatment (Table A 3).

Table A 3- costs of treatment

	Total costs	Care product code
Radiotherapy	€ 8275	990061072, 990061014
Open Prostatectomy	€ 9780	20109012

Costs of treatments less than € 850 were extracted using the care product code and the tariff tool developed by CZ (<https://www.cz.nl/service-en-contact/zoek-tarieven>). For post-treatment costs we assumed 4 consultations and prostate specific antigen (PSA) tests per anno in the first two years, and 2 per anno after that (Table A 4).

Table A 4- post-treatment costs

Year	Quantity p.a		Price/unit	Total costs		Care product code
	1-2	>2		1-2	>2	
Consultation fee	4	2	€ 122 (15)	€ 488 (30)	€ 244 (21)	20109088
PSA test	4	2	€ 5,8	€ 23,2	€ 11,6	72621
Total				€ 511,2 (30)	€ 255,6 (21)	

Costs of medication was taken from a website, <https://www.farmacotherapeutischkompas.nl>, that reports the costs of pharmaceutical healthcare. At the suspicion of biochemical failure or metastatic disease, a PSMA scan can be made. If recurrence has taken place, the patient can receive secondary localized treatment, or hormonal therapy. Once the patient progresses to castrate resistant metastatic disease, the patient is treated with chemotherapy (Table A 5).

Table A 5- costs metastatic disease

	Quantity p. a	Price/unit (SD)	Total costs (SD)	Care product code
Consultation fee specialist	4	€ 122 (15)	€ 488 (21)	20109088
LHRH agonist leuprorelin	4	€ 450 (125)	€ 1800 (250)	20109010
Docetaxel	6	€ 721 (120)	€ 4326 (294)	20109050
Prednisolon	6	€ 18	€ 108	
PSMA-scan	0,35	€ 1060 (123)	€ 371 (73)	120501
Zoledronic acid	4	€ 422 (40)	€ 1688 (80)	
Total			€ 8781 (401)	

SD: standard deviation; p.a; per anno

For the management of late erectile dysfunction, we assumed that half the patients use medication, 10% of the patients use cavernous injections and 5% use a vacuum pump. We estimated that medication or injections would be used on average once a month, and that the vacuum pump lasts two years (Table A 6)

Table A 6- costs of the management of erectile dysfunction

	<i>Quantity p. a</i>	<i>Price/unit</i>	<i>Total costs</i>
Sildenafil	6	€ 6,83 (2)	€ 41 (5)
Cavernous injection	1,2	€ 11,06 (3)	€ 13 (3)
Vacuum pump	0,025	€ 235 (35)	€ 6 (6,5)
Total			€ 60 (9)

For the management of late urinary incontinence, we estimate that approximately three quarters of patients use physiotherapy, with 8 sessions per year. We estimate that 90% of the patients with urinary incontinence use pads 3 times a day. We assume that 5% requires diapers once a day, and all patients who use diapers or pads require net trousers. It is estimated that 2,5% require drainage bags, of which they will require bed bags and leg bags (Table A 7). For the prices of medical products such as pads, net trousers and leg bags, we collected costs from different websites such as www.mediqcombicare.nl, www.pharmamarket.nl, and www.123drogisterij.nl.

Table A 7- costs of the management of urinary incontinence

	<i>Quantity p. a</i>	<i>Price/unit</i>	<i>Total costs</i>
Physiotherapy	1	€ 35 (0,6)	€ 35 (0,6)
Balloon catheter	0,05	€ 12 (0,3)	€ 0,6 (0,07)
Pads	394	€ 0,36 (1)	€ 142 (20)
Diapers	18	€ 0,65 (0,08)	€ 11,7 (0,3)
Net trousers	0,95	€ 1,25 (0,1)	€ 1,2 (0,1)
Bed bag, sterile	3	€ 20 (0,7)	€ 60 (1,2)
Leg bag, sterile	1,3	€ 40 (1)	€ 52 (1,1)
Total			€ 302,5 (21)

Rectal bleeding is mostly treated with low cost treatments such as medication, but a low percentage has severe rectal bleeding and needs to be treated with infrared coagulation or a coloscopy (Table A 8)

Table A 8- costs of the management of rectal bleeding

	<i>Quantity p. a</i>	<i>Price/unit</i>	<i>Total costs</i>	<i>Care product code</i>
Salofalk/ Arestal	36,5	€ 1,13 (1)	€ 41 (6)	
Sclerosis, Rubber band ligation, infrared coagulation	0,05	€ 167 (3,8)	€ 8 (0,8)	35135
Intervention-coloscopy	0,05	€ 469 (7)	€ 23,5 (1,6)	34697
Sigmoidoscopy	0,05	€ 445 (34)	€ 22 (8)	34686
Total			€ 94,5 (10)	

Appendix III – Distribution for the generation of synthetic dataset

<i>Parameter name</i>	<i>Distribution type</i>			<i>Ref</i>
Age (years)	Normal	$\mu = 60$	$\sigma = 10$	[1–5]
PSA (ng/mL)	Beta	$\alpha = 4.17$	$\beta = 51.5$	[1–5]
BMI (kg/m ²)	Normal	$\mu = 28$	$\sigma = 3$	[3–5]
T-stage	Step	T1 = 66%	T2 = 34%	[1, 3–5]
neg. biopsy cores (N)	Normal	$\mu = 4.5$	$\sigma = 1.9$	[2]
pos. biopsy cores (N)	Half normal	Location = 1	Scale = 2.46	[2]
P. Gleason grade	Beta	4 = 14%	3 = 86%	[1, 3, 4]
S. Gleason grade	Step	4 = 19%	3 = 71%	[2]
ADT given	Step	no = 22%	yes = 78%	[1]
ADT length	Beta	$\alpha = 0.125$	$\beta = 1.25$	[1]
ASA score	Step	I/II = 18%	III/IV = 82%	[1, 3]
Nerve sparing	Step	no = 81%	yes = 19%	[4]
Abdominal surgery	Step	no = 90.3%	yes = 9.7%	[6]
HRQOL (%)	Beta	$\alpha = 1.5$	$\beta = 6$	[5]
Membranous urethra length (mm)	Normal	$\mu = 12$	$\sigma = 3$	[4]
Mean Trigone dose (Gy)	Normal	$\mu = 68$	$\sigma = 6$	[3]
V75 rectum (%)	Gamma	location = 1	scale = 4	[6]

Ref: reference; PSA: prostate specific antigen; BMI: body mass index; T-stage: Tumor stage; N neg.: number of negative; N pos.: number of positive; P.: Primary; S.: Secondary; ADT: androgen deprivation therapy; ASA: American Society of Anesthesiologists; PN: Pelvic nodes; HRQOL: sexual health-related quality of life; V75: percentage receiving at least 75 Gray; Gy = Gray

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Appendix IV – distribution of clinical parameters in synthetic dataset

<i>Parameter name</i>	<i>EBRT (SD)</i>	<i>RP (SD)</i>	<i>P</i>
Age (years)	63.8 (10.7)	58.8 (9.1)	<<0.001
PSA (ng/mL)	8.3 (3.5)	6.8 (3.5)	<<0.001
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.9 (2.9)	28.0 (3.0)	0.81
T-stage 2 (%)	48.7	24.4	<<0.001
neg. biopsy cores (N)	3.7 (1.8)	4.8 (1.8)	<<0.001
pos. biopsy cores (N)	3.5 (1.7)	2.7 (1.4)	<<0.001
P. Gleason grade 4 (%)	27.1	3.3	<<0.001
S. Gleason grade 4 (%)	14.7	20.9	0.01
ADT given (%)	79.8	80.0	0.72
ADT length (months)	19.0 (27.5)	4.1 (9.9)	<<0.001
ASA score >II (%)	86.2	78.9	0.003
Nerve sparing (%)	12.4	27.5	0.001
Abdominal surgery (%)	6.4	11.6	0.005
HRQOL (%)	82.9 (12.3)	76.9 (14.6)	<<0.001
Membranous urethra length (mm)	11.8 (3.0)	12.1 (2.8)	0.04
Mean Trigone dose (Gy)	67.2 (6.0)	68.4 (5.7)	0.001
V75 rectum (%)	3.8 (3.9)	4.5 (4.6)	0.008

EBRT: external beam radiotherapy; RP: radical prostatectomy; SD: standard deviation; PSA: prostate specific antigen; BMI: body mass index; T-stage: Tumor stage; N neg.: number of negative; N pos.: number of positive; P.: Primary; S.: Secondary; ADT: androgen deprivation therapy; ASA: American Society of Anesthesiologists; PN: Pelvic nodes; HRQOL: sexual health-related quality of life; V75: percentage receiving at least 75 Gray; Gy = Gray

Appendix V – benchmark study including clinical parameters reported

<i>Study</i>	<i>Treatment [N]</i>	<i>Parameters</i>	<i>Outcome</i>	<i>Value</i>	<i>Model</i>		
Hamdy 2016	EBRT [545]	Age (years)	62	5 year BDFS	88.5%	89.0%	
		GS 7	21%				
		T2	25%				
		PSA <10	90%				
		PSA ng/ml	4.7				
RP [553]	RP [553]	Age (years)	62	5 year BDFS	88.1%	87.0%	
		GS 7	21%				
		T2	25%				
		PSA <10	90%				
		PSA ng/ml	4.7				
CHHiP	74 Gy [1065]	Age (years)	69	5 year BDFS	88.5%	88.4%	
		T2	58%				
		GS 7	64%				
		ADT	83%				
		ADT months	6.2				
	60 Gy [1074]	60 Gy [1074]	Age (years)	69	5 year BDFS	91.3%	89.9%
			T2	58%			
			GS 7	63%			
			ADT	85%			
			ADT months	6.2			
57 Gy [1077]	57 Gy [1077]	Age (years)	69	5 year BDFS	86.8%	87.9%	
		T2	58%				
		GS 7	65%				
		ADT	84%				
		ADT months	6.2				
Donovan 2016	EBRT [545]	Age (years)	62	6 month UI	5%	3.3%	
		GS 7	20%	6 year UI	3.5%	3.3%	
		T2	21%	6 month ED	77.8%	85.4%	
		PSA (ng/ml)	4.8	6 year ED	72.6%	71.6%	
				6 month RB	3.8%	14.7%	
	RP [553]	RP [553]	Age (years)	62	6 year RB	5.6%	5.7%
					6 month UI	46%	41.5%
					6 year UI	17%	17.0%
					6 month ED	88%	92.7%
					6 year ED	83.5%	83.7%

N: number of patients; EBRT: external beam radiotherapy; RP: radical prostatectomy; BDFS: biological disease free survival; UI: urinary incontinence; ED: erectile dysfunction; RB: rectal bleeding; Gy: gray; GS: gleason score; PSA: prostate specific antigen in ng/ml; ADT: androgen deprivation therapy

Appendix VI

Univariate one-way sensitivity analyses were performed to examine the impact of individual parameters on the results, of which the fifteen most impactful parameters are graphically represented in a tornado plot (Figure A 5). In the diagram we varied each parameter between the 2.5 and 97.5 percentiles and calculated the resulting iNMB of the DSS compared to the randomized treatment allotment strategy. The most impactful parameter is the utility value of erectile dysfunction, but over the range of these parameters the iNMB of the DSS was still positive, and thus cost-effective when compared to the randomized strategy.

Figure A 5- This figure shows the impact of individual parameters on the incremental net monetary benefit of a decision support system versus randomized treatment. The vertical line represents the deterministic run. ED = erectile dysfunction; OR = odds ratio; BED = biologically effective dose; RB = rectal bleeding; HRQoL = health related quality of life

To test the robustness of the model results, we varied some key assumptions in the model, of which the results are shown in Table A 9. Over the different scenarios the DSS kept a high probability of being cost-effective.

Table A 9- The results of the different scenario analyses

Scenario	Value	TCP diff (%) [95% CI]	Cost diff (€) [95% CI]	QALY diff (years) [95% CI]	P CE (%)
Discount rate	0%	1.5 [-2.9-5.9]	-478 [-657--324]	0.15 [-0.01-0.29]	99.2
	5%	1.5 [-2.9-5.9]	-296 [-396--196]	0.09 [0.01-0.18]	99.8
	10%	1.5 [-2.9-5.9]	-200 [-265--135]	0.07 [0.00-0.13]	98.6
Dose plan ¹	2.5x28	1.8 [-3.6 -7.3]	-614 [-1376--148]	0.09 [-0.22-0.41]	79.4
	2x35	2.0 [-2.2-6.2]	-147[-832-538]	0.19 [-0.19-0.56]	88.0
	2x37	1.5 [-2.9-5.9]	-308 [-425--192]	0.13 [0.01-0.25]	99.4
Time horizon	5	1.5 [-2.9-5.9]	-78 [-106-50]	0.03 [-0.01-0.07]	97.2
	10	1.5 [-2.9-5.9]	-173[-229--117]	0.07 [-0.00-0.15]	99.2
	15	1.5 [-2.9-5.9]	-260 [-347--172]	0.09 [0.00-0.18]	99.0
	50	1.5 [-2.9-5.9]	-418 [-561--274]	0.17 [-0.00-0.35]	98.6

Costs DSS	20	1.5 [-2.9-5.9]	-304 [-414--194]	0.12 [0.01-0.23]	99.6
	100	1.5 [-2.9-5.9]	-224 [-334--114]	0.17 [-0.0-0.33]	98.6
	250	1.5 [-2.9-5.9]	-74 [-184-26]	0.17 [-0.0-0.33]	99.4
	500	1.5 [-2.9-5.9]	176 [66-286]	0.17 [-0.0-0.33]	99.4

CI = confidence interval; P = probability; EBRT = external beam radiotherapy; DSS = decision support system

¹ Fraction dose x the number of fractions

Figure A 6- the cost-effectiveness acceptability curve (CEAC) comparing the randomized treatment allotment strategy to the full decision support system (DSS), and a simplified DSS that utilized only age, prostate specific antigen (PSA) and T-stage.

To test the usefulness of our advanced DSS, we tested a simplified DSS using only three clinical parameters: age, t-stage, and PSA. The simplified DSS had a large probability (85.1%) of being cost-effective compared to the randomized treatment allotment strategy. However, compared to the original DSS, the simplified DSS only had a 16.3% chance of being cost-effective. We expanded the simplified DSS with three extra parameters, including primary Gleason score, diabetes and prior abdominal surgery, and found that this simplified DSS had a 89.1% probability of being cost-effective compared to the randomized strategy, so 4% better than the 3 parameter DSS. However, this 6 parameter DSS still only outperforms the full DSS in 21.1% of the simulations (Figure A 6).